

CAREX PACHYSTYLIS

Safarova Zakiya Teshayevna¹

Lecturer at the Department of Biology

Asadova Nilufar Yorkinovna²

4th year student

¹⁻²Bukhara State University, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7028189>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th August 2022

Accepted: 22nd August 2022

Online: 27th August 2022

KEY WORDS

deserts, plains, steppes, river deltas, foothills, mountains, desert sedge, fodder plant, Asteraceae, legumes, grasses, Liliaceae, cruciferous, umbellate, haze, lily, buckwheat, clove, borage, rosacea.

The vegetation of Central Asia is incredibly diverse and rich. Here, deserts and plains, steppes and river deltas, foothills and mountains form not only a peculiar landscape, but also determine the diversity of species. Few people know that a large number of plants grow in Central Asia. It may seem incredible, but in reality, compared with the central regions of Russia and even with the taiga, in the foothill and mountainous regions of Central Asia, the number of plants per unit area is many times greater.

The total amount of vegetation, of course, is greater on the plains of many countries, but in terms of the overall diversity of species, Central Asia is ahead of many regions of the world. The richest flora of Central Asia includes more than 6,000 species of different plants. Plant

ABSTRACT

the article presents data on the flora of Central Asia, especially the flora of Uzbekistan, ephemeral plants growing in the arid steppe areas of Uzbekistan. The plant described is thick columnar sedge, or desert sedge, botany and physiology, economic and fodder features of the plant.

communities are most strongly developed in foothill and mountainous regions. The main reason for the richness and diversity here is the altitudinal zonality of the relief, where each altitudinal zone is represented by its unique climate and weather conditions, soils, and different regimes for the development of plants.

In Central Asia, deserts, steppes and mountains coexist side by side. In the deserts and steppes grows its own, special, adapted to the dry and dry climate of the vegetation cover. Tugai vegetation is widespread along the rivers and along the shores of lakes. In the mountains, the diversity is very large. Here you can distinguish several tiers, each of which grows its own unique flora. At the same time, they talk about the so-called belt type of vegetation.

The complex topography of the mountains, its slopes with different exposure, facing different directions of the world, receiving a different portion of illumination, weathered and moistened with different intensity, have a strong influence on the distribution of various species. In addition, the composition of the soil, which directly depends on the steepness of the slopes and altitudinal zonality, also largely determines the diversity and diversity of the vegetation cover.

Uzbekistan is located in the center of Central Asia and is included in the arid (dry) zone of the Earth. The northern and western parts of Uzbekistan are occupied by the plains of the Turan lowland, the southern and eastern parts by the Tien Shan and Pamir-Alay mountain ranges. The landscapes of Uzbekistan are diverse - these are deserts, mountains, steppes, tugai-reed thickets in floodplains. Vegetation cover of Uzbekistan includes about 4230 species, 1028 genera from 138 families. Among them - 492 cultivated and cultivated plants from 79 families. About 577 wild-growing species are medicinal plants.

Compositae, legumes, cereals, labiales, cruciferous, umbellate, haze, lily, buckwheat, clove, borage, rosaceous are the richest in species in the flora of the

republic. The complexity and unevenness of the relief determines the diversity of the vegetation cover. In Uzbekistan, four high-altitude fields can be distinguished, each of which has its own specific type of vegetation. Deserts and plains - "chul", foothills and hills - "adyr", mountains - "tau", highlands - "yaylau (jaylau)".

Sandy deserts (Most of the Kyzylkum desert, Sundukli and Kattakum sands). In sandy deserts, species such as djuzgun, saxaul, sedge, sand acacia, Richter's saltwort, astragalus, cone-bearing cone-bearing conifer, little-toothed ragwort, and haze are common. Many of the plants have long roots, rhizomes, which prevent the mobility of sands in the desert.

We are conducting research work on the plant thick-columnar sedge, or simply like desert sedge.

Thick-columned sedge, or Desert sedge - *Carex pachystylis* - is a perennial herbaceous plant, a species of the genus Sedge -*Carex*, of the sedge family - Cyperaceae. It is an exceptionally valuable pasture forage with a high nutritional value. Thick-columnar sedge is an evergreen plant with a straight stem 4 to 30 cm long and a rhizome up to 6 m long. The leaves are flat, shorter than the stems. Spikelets (4-6 pieces) crowded into a dense rhombic head.

Desert sedge - *Carex pachystylis*

SEDGE- with rhizomes

The plant is found in the Caucasus (Armenia), North Africa (Egypt), Western Asia (Afghanistan, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Syria, Turkey), and in Central Asia (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan).

It develops well on loamy, clayey and sandy loam soils. It is widely

distributed in piedmont deserts, forming together with bulbous bluegrass (*Poa bulbosa*) ephemeral pastures. In the absence of grazing or with moderate grazing, bluegrass displaces, and with excessive grazing, the dominance passes to bluegrass.

Ash and nutrient content (NITROGEN-FREE EXTRACTIVE SUBSTANCES)

Phase	From absolute dry matter to %				
	ash	protein	fat	fiber	NFES
Before flowering	9,3	22,8	5,3	18,8	43,8

flowering	7,6	19,0	3,3	20,5	49,6
Fruiting	8,5	15,4	3,6	23,5	49,0
dry plant	8,2	8,4	2,6	28,6	52,2
winter plant	10,2	7,5	2,3	34,6	45,4

For 100 kg of dry matter at the end of flowering, there are 102.1 feed units and 8.5 kg of digestible protein. Dry summer

plants contain 51.7 feed units and 2.6 digestible protein.

The formation of a pillow by the Sedge plant

In Uzbekistan, and especially in the Bukhara region, astrakhan sheep tend to huddle more in the steppe. Desert sedge is one of the best spring food in the desert. In green and dry form, it is eaten by all kinds of farm animals and especially by horses and sheep. When eaten together with bluegrass, animals recover and gain fat

after winter. Dry remains during the summer and winter are eaten satisfactorily. The plant tolerates moderate trampling well. In a favorable spring, after grazing, it can give 30-40% of the aftermath of the original stock. In the city it is used as an evergreen, ornamental plant.

References:

1. Губанов.И. и др. 644. *Capsella bursa-pastoris* (L.) Medik. — Сумочник пастуший, или Пастушья сумка // Иллюстрированный определитель растений Средней России. В 3 т. — М.:
2. Дудченко Л. Г., Козьяков А. С., Кривенко В. В. Пряно-ароматические и пряно-вкусовые растения: Справочник / Отв. ред. К. М. Сытник. — К.: Наукова думка, 1989. — 304 с.
3. Сафарова З. Т., Шамсиева Ш., Фармонова О. ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ РАСТЕНИЯ РАПС //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 522-525.
4. Сафарова З. Т., Фармонова О. С. К. МЕДОНОСНЫЕ РАСТЕНИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА //Scientific progress. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 1083-1084.
5. Руднянская Е. И. Пыльцевая продуктивность некоторых растений // Пчеловодство : журнал.